

THE CHANGE OF THE ADDED MASS AND ITS EFFECTS ON GOVERNING EQUATIONS 2ND VERESION

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ABSTRACT

The first version of this article created eruption of reactions which mandated a change. While this author mistakenly was under impression that he was the first discovering effect of the added mass change, this effect was noticed earlier. Previously, the added mass change was noticed due to the body volume change (change in the sphere volume). This author noticed the added mass change because the change of orientation and deformation. This article discusses the added mass change due to all the reasons such as the size, deformation, orientation. Regardless for the reason for the added mass change, the effects of the change must be generated.

The added mass change reveals itself, for example, when a moving ship is stricken or pushed from the side or even when the rudder is changing its angle, or change in volume in aquatic bodies. The change has several effects such change the location of the pivot point, and change the body velocity (acceleration). The added mass change can increase several times ship's mass and thus ship velocity can be reduced substantially. The added mass change due to a change in body shape used by aquatic bodies increase the speed. There is no other explanation could explain this strange occurrences.

As it will be discussed here, the added mass change extracts or requires energy from the body. Thus, additional terms in governing equation are required to account for this phenomenon in the fluid domain. In fact, this is one of the possible reasons for the instabilities reported in the literature in the calculations of fluid domain.

NOMENCLATURE

A Cross Section Area

B Buoyancy force
 g Gravity constant
 k Spring constant
 m_a The (fish) added mass
 m_b The (fish) mass
 R The resistance
 t Time
 x Distance in straight (movement) direction
 ρ density
 θ angle

Key Words

Added Mass Change, Added Mass Energy Conservation, Roll, Marine Navigation, Fish Locomotion

1 Introduction

After the publishing the first version of this article, a flurries of communication about this material commenced. The corrections to the material are due to these avalanche of comments and exposure of new experimental proofs. This unorthodox publication seem to be appropriate because as the first version was deficient and did not containing all the needed materials. Apparently, the idea of the change of the added mass has been before this author but with the relationship to the change of body size or deformation never in regard to orientation. Furthermore, one element of the implications was discussed in by Giorgio et al (2017). Giorgio et al suggested that the added mass could increases the velocity of the body and here it will be expended and this will be discussed. For example, the new concept of added momentum and the added moment of inertia will defined here.

People were aware of the change in the added mass for example, Bainbridge's experiment (1963) his data showed that the value of added mass can be simplified as $m_a = 1/4 \pi / \rho d^2$, where d is the depth. Bainbridge measurements show that the added mass also depends on time. This fact demonstrates that fish's deformation (and maybe the orientation) affects the added mass. Lighthill's data (1971) revealed that the added mass value (coefficient) is around one and it is fluctuating about 25%. It worth noting that the limit of the change of added mass in this case which is about 25%. This limit is a positive indication for the maximum extraction of energy (or momentum) by caudal fin (tail) which indirectly demonstrates the added mass change effect.

A string of papers dealing with the added mass change due to change of the size mostly with a spherical shape appeared in the literature for example (Weymouth and Triantafyllou 2013; Weymouth, Subramaniam, and Triantafyllou 2015). In these papers the motivation was to understand how the octopus and/or aquatic bodies increase their speed in a critical maneuvering (hunting or hunted). In this paper, the focus is on the theoretical aspects of the added mass change. Hence, attempt is made to understand the underlying principles behind the change of added mass. In these papers, it was suggested that the added mass momentum (they referred to this lost differently) is "lost" when body added mass reduced and should be added as an external force on the right side (of the equations) for the body movement. This approach is the upper limit to maximum force obtained by the added mass change. While these authors did realize it, they actually invented the added momentum concept. As the found papers were dealing with the added mass change implications Giorgio et al (2017) study the effects of the change volume of during the spherical shape movement (see fig. 3).

The current investigation started because the interest in the energy lost during the added mass change. Google Scholar shows that about 0.5 million articles were written on for energy related to marine or ships. Many of these articles deal with the energy and some with the auxiliary material not related topics such as environmental impact especially the CO_2 omission. These articles discuss several possible sources of the ship energy loss such as wind (weather), resistance (to the hull), energy efficiency of the propellers, (added external sources), modifying ship navigation path. This discussion deals with the resistance to the hull design. The hull design has several elements or issues such as coating, geometry, etc. Here, the focus is on the one of the elements that contributes to the energy loss. This element is the added mass change contribution which is a significant and yet it is ignored. Example of this obvious is Pacuraru (2022) describes various energy losses without even not mentioning this loss. In addition, the energy of aquatic bodies has a maximum output because of this effect. A large change of the added mass indicates possible large energy loss.

Up to 60 years ago or so the added mass was ignored and

the governing equations were built with this assumption for the fish locomotion and the surface vehicles. At least with this omission, the equations were consistent. Currently, this assumption has been challenged (transformation is not complete yet) and it has been replaced by the governing equations that partially include the added mass. The consistency was broken and now the governing equations are using the added mass but yet in the same time the properties such as the moment of inertia are calculated as if the added mass does not exist. In the previous papers in this series, the lens were placed on the rotation pivot points and defined the centroid of the added mass. While in certain cases the added mass change is obvious such as as the body change yet in other situations the added mass is not so obvious. In this discussion an attempt is made to remove the cloak created by the added mass coefficients at least for major points. This effect shows that there is a change in the added mass and hence there should be an additional term in the fluid governing equation.

The representation of the added mass coefficients while ignoring the issue of the total added mass is exclusive¹ practice in the study of biology especially in the area of aquatic locomotion and surface vehicles area. The usage of added mass coefficients cloaks the fact that while the added mass coefficients are constant, the total added mass varies during the maneuvering of the body. In fact, this change is so significant that it limits the ability of the aquatic body to produce propulsion.

To analysis the energy losses, two situations are compared one) without added mass and two) with the added mass. In order to avoid complications in this analysis, this discussion of the change of direction is limited on the momentum's effects. The simple pendulum and/or the standard spring mass systems are considered as a first approximation as systems where the energy is conserved. Thus, systems that are similar to spring-mass also can be considered to be systems where energy is conserved. In these systems, the energy changes from one form of energy to another. For example, in the spring-mass system the energy moves between the kinetic energy and (spring) potential energy. Additional example, a ship undergoes a very small angle rotation (roll) which can be approximated as "pendulum". In this analysis, the mathematical complications of the double pendulum are ignored to clarify the abstraction of the core energy conservation issues.

In the schizophrenic approach commonly used for aquatic creatures and on surface vehicles, on one hand, (Bar-Meir 2023) the added mass and the added moment of inertia are considered, yet, and on the other hand, the calculations of the location of pivot currently has been based on neglecting the added mass contribution. Several examples come to mind to demonstrate this schizophrenic belief is (Pérez-Canosa, Orosa, Galdo, and Barros 2022). Beside this blindside the paper demonstrate several other errors such as energy loss etc. Another example which more de-

¹Perhaps in other area it also occurred.

pressing: a senior administrator and a teacher Carolyn Judge in United States Naval Academy believes in this schizophrenic approach as shown in her class notes. She further, stated in class notes that “[s]o, in reality, although the actual roll pivot point is generally the center of flotation, the center of gravity provides a simple, approximate alternative.” While she believes that pivot point is at the center of flotation (probably she means to the buoyancy centroid) and mass centroid is good approximation. None of these points are really the pivot point. The most scary part that she even do consider (examine) the actually pivot point. It is beyond her, maybe? The effects of the change of the rotation pivot points are far more than just the effects of the size of the moment of inertia. Each of the added mass coefficients used to evaluate the motion for each direction as a matrix of elements. When examining this matrix, one cannot notice that the total added mass changes. All the coefficients are constant. However, when the body moves along, let say, in the surge direction the body will have the minimum added mass. Yet, when the body moves in the sway direction the added mass is significantly larger for a typical marine body. Hence, even under this approach the total added mass is changing during the process and total added mass is a function of the time (orientation). The amount of added mass changes, hence the energy amount in the system (body and added mass) changes.

What happen to the transferred energy to the fluid (in the case of reduction of the added mass)? Clearly, the energy of the body and added mass system is not conserved. The first law of thermodynamics dictates that this energy is not really lost. The energy is “transferred” to the liquid. The transfer is not actual transfer but remove of the link between the movement of the body and the fluid elements. At that point, the added mass element movements aren’t dictated by the body movements any more, and the energy of this element has the “permission” to dissipate. Stating in a different form, the meaning of added mass element is that represented fluid element is no longer tied to the body movement. The fluid element is tied to the boundary conditions, and the energy of the element can be dissipated. Conversely in the case of increase in the added mass, to keep the movement of the element, the body (the forces that moves the body) must supply additional energy (forces). If energy isn’t available, the velocity of the body (and the added mass) is reduced. So, there is an unsymmetrical reaction to the added mass change. For the increase of the added mass, the body will slow down. While for the case of reduction of the added mass, the velocity remains constant (unless the force is reduces).

Taking another view, suppose that a body travels in the x direction with a small added mass coefficient suddenly gain a acceleration/velocity component in y direction with large added mass coefficient. In the case, the body initially had a certain velocity or energy. The energy remains constant but the total mass increases, thus the total velocity must be reduced (conservation of momentum or energy). At that point, the ship or surface vehi-

cle will be slower. This can be observed in many videos shown on youtube.

The answer to the question why was this change (in regard to orientation reason and some extend to the deformation) in the energy and the momentum was not noticed by any researchers before is very obvious. This energy transfer was cloaked by the added mass coefficients. The added mass coefficients are constant and independent of the ship orientation and hence they provide the illusion that everything is constant. Even those who believe in the schizophrenic added mass acknowledge that the total added mass is not constant indirectly. This fact can be observed from the construction of the governing equations where these added mass coefficients multiply the velocity (acceleration) components which change. Thus when one of these added mass coefficients, for example, turn off, the total added mass changes.

One of consequences of this analysis is the following scenario: a coin place in fast stream of inviscid liquid in the narrow side. The coin will not move because the flow is inviscid. However when the coin changes the orientation to the largest width suddenly the coin will forced to accelerate. Note there is no viscosity and due to D’Alembert’s paradox the pressure does not affect the coin and yet there will be acceleration. The reason that the added mass that joined (due to) the coin has large energy (velocity) and this energy will accelerate the coin. In fact, it was observed that octopus and other aquatic bodies using this technique to accelerate during important maneuvering.

This discussion is an exploration of the relationship between the added mass, m_a , or the added moment of inertia, and the lost energy. This situation is very common in real life. For example, when a fish moves its tail (caudal fin) the added mass changes and thus the fish loss energy beside the energy to propel the body. This back and forth movements of the caudal fin continuously change the added mass and hence causes energy loss which has nothing to do with the desired purpose. All the research to date, that this author aware of, ignore this mechanism (Brafield 1985). The only exception is the effect of the change of volume on the added mass.

2 Relationship of Loss Energy and Added Property

The focus here is on establishing the relationship between the energy with the added mass insulated and isolated from the other physical phenomena. While the gravity force is important for the energy conservation in spring–mass system, yet it does not affect energy conservation nor the frequency for the spring–mass system only the location of the equilibrium point. Similarly while the spring–mass system on a flat surface and the spring–mass hanged on spring system are different yet they ended with the same ODE even though gravity affects only the hanged system. Thus, they are mentioned but pushed to the background. These forces do not change the arguments for the energy conservation discussion.

FIGURE 1. Heave motion for spring mass system

The standard comparison of the internal forces with the external forces provides a regular spring–mass second order ODE (neglecting the damping) which can be written as

$$m_b \frac{dx}{dt} + kx + \dots + m_b g - B = 0 \quad (1)$$

where m_b is the body mass, k is the spring constant, g is the gravity constant and B is the buoyancy constant (notice that it should have x inside but it is ignored). This equation is result from examining the forces that act regardless the energy. Below is the proof that the energy is conserved for this system. Note that velocity is given by $U = dx/dt$ and for the simplicity sake, the buoyancy and gravity are ignored. The proof is done by assuming that the energy is constant and compering the governing equations of the two cases (energy and forces). If the equations are identical, it is the proof. The energy in the system is

$$\frac{m_b}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + \frac{kx^2}{2} = constant \quad (2)$$

In the case where the mass, m_b , is constant with respect to time, the differentiation produces

$$\frac{m_b}{2} \cancel{\left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + \frac{k}{2} \cancel{x} \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Note the second derivative is the internal derivative of the velocity. Equation (3) becomes identical to eq. (1) which indicts that the energy is conserved.

What happened when the idealized situation changes because the added mass value changes during the process? Can the energy including the added mass remains either potential or purely kinetic constant? Equation (2), the masses includes, $m_a + m_b$ body mass and the added liquid mass can be written as

following

$$\frac{(m_b + m_a)}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + \frac{kx^2}{2} = constant \quad (4)$$

If the system is made of the body and the moving liquid (assuming that the added mass: liquid amount is finite and moving with a uniform velocity) is a closed system (does not exchange energy with surroundings) then the energy can be assumed to be conserved. With absence of the viscosity (a fundamental assumption here), the energy in the liquid continues to move with the body. The meaning of the term close system here refers to a close container and not to the regular thermodynamics meaning. The open system, as oppose to close system, is without a physical barrier. For open system, the energy is dispersed via different mechanisms. Again, the buoyancy and gravity are “pushed” to the background.

The left hand side is equal to a constant under the assumptions above thus differentiating yields

$$(m_b + m_a) \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \left(\frac{dm_a}{dt} \right) \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + kx \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + \dots = 0 \quad (5)$$

canceling the velocity dx/dt (the velocity is not zero) results in

$$(m_b + m_a) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \left(\frac{dm_a}{dt} \right) \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + kx + \dots = 0 \quad (6)$$

If the initial eq. (1) is to be believed, then clearly eq. (6) is not correct in the sense that both equations cannot be correct in the same time. The term for the second derivative contains the added (liquid) and body mass, $(m_a + m_b)$. The first term with body mass, m_b , is visibly part that energy conserved while the added mass part, m_a , is guessable. The term guessable is used here to indicate that it is not part of the proof and it isn’t proved to be a loss. The added (liquid) mass velocity is not uniform (as it idealized) which cannot be recorded. However, the second term, the energy is not conserved at all because in physical terms is related to change of the added mass (liquid) which there is no mechanism that make it any way retrievable or transferable. The added mass, as it can be observed from fig. 1, is changing during along the x coordinate. For example, when body is totally out of the liquid, the added mass is about zero, while the added mass will have the maximum value when the whole body is immersed. This energy is a lost during the process (at least in the regards to the system of the body plus the added mass).

The exterior forces that act on the floating body are the buoyancy, gravity (the surface tension is ignored). The net exterior forces on the moving system is zero if the liquid surface remains constant. Then the governing equation can be written as

$$(m_a + m_b) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + kx = \frac{dm_a}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} \quad (7)$$

From mathematical point of view the right hand side eq. (7) looks like a dissipation term. Yet, numerically it can be treated as exterior force calculated from the previous step.

Three possible energy terms or mathematical expressions were analyzed. These expressions represent the part where the energy can be conserved and when the energy possibly can be conserved and when it does not conserved at all. In this case, the energy that associated with the body is conserved while the energy that the fluid “acquires” can be conserved. In any situation, the energy that associated with change of the added mass is free to get lost.

3 The Notation of the ship movement

FIGURE 2. The common names for the ship movements.

4 The Effects On The Governing Equations

An empty cart that moves at a constant velocity suddenly loaded with a large mass (let say a large rock) with the surroundings velocity, the cart will have a sudden change in the velocity. The change of the cart velocity depends the difference between of the surroundings velocity and the cart’s velocity. If the change is small, the effect is small. The same logic can be applied to the change of the added mass. The fish relative velocity can be very large in case of hunting (escaping or catching). The fish goes through several transitions in which the added mass increases or decrease continuously. If a fish caudal fin (tail) at a straight line and the fish bends the tail bends, the added mass increases. At

that situation, the fish applies force but also increases its total mass (the added mass). In fact at that stage, the force has an element (part of the force) against the velocity and also increases the added mass which both reduce the fish velocity.

Consider a case where the fish bend his tail in a significant amount then changes its body to be a straight line. The added mass decreases in a very substantial amount. The difference in the added mass is significant and visible. The velocity field around the fish must change to match to existence of the new (increase) added mass to accommodate the change in the fish body shape. There are two states added mass one before the movement and one after the movement or the change of the body. The difference in the steady state between these two states is the extra energy the fluid field “gained” or “lost”. Idelsohn et al (2009) reported many stability problems caused by the added mass calculations. In fact Idelsohn et al described three different mechanisms or scenarios for which the added mass creates numerical instabilities. It is impossible to examine if these instabilities are caused by the change added mass. Admittedly, the descriptions in the paper are cloud and clear enough for this author (the excess usage of jargon prevent this author and others to understand or even guess what really meant in the writing may be they did want other to read it.) from checking the analysis of these cases.

Since the fish location was discussed, it worth to mention the energy efficiency or the possible maximum extracted energy. To generate propulsion, the fish needs on one hand to swing the tail at the largest angle (as much as possible) and create propulsion (Bar-Meir 2022b; Bar-Meir 2022c; Bar-Meir 2022d). Yet, on the other hand, the fish needs to minimize the swing as much as possible to reduce the energy loss due to the added mass effect (and negative forces). Thus, there might be one or more maximum(s) to which the fish can use. Clearly the first maximum is more likely to occur.

The two steady state situations before the change denoted as “0” and after the change denoted as “1” which are base to determine how much energy should change. Equation (6) suggests that $-dm_a/dt U_0$ can be moved to the right hand side and be used as a known force that act on the body to alleviate and improve the accuracy and account for the energy change. For rapidly change (what is rapid in this case?) only part of term can be used in every step of the calculations and should be considered semi or somewhat transitional. In that value (difference between “0” and “1”) should be multiply by a coefficient smaller than one and the leftover energy should assume to be dissipated.

5 Change of Volume Case

Giorgio et al (2017) have conducted an experimental study on the effects of the change of added mass due to the change in the sphere volume. Giorgio et al used a spherical balloon as a changing added mass moving body that moves through a fixed

FIGURE 3. The drawing of the experiment shown change volume sphere after Giorgio et al. Point (4) shows the rails point (2) depicts permanent holder point (1) the moving part. Point (6) is the sphere that change the volume.

depth as shown in fig. 3. This experiment intend to study how the octopus and bodies like that using the change of the volume to gain an extra acceleration. The main mechanism of the octopus is achieved by pushing a liquid jet and hence gaining momentum forward. The additional mechanism to gain extra acceleration is done by changing its body size (change of volume). The focus here is on the added mass, hence this element will examined. Consider the control volume which include the body and added mass. As oppose to the experiments, the body is free to move. Only material that leaves the control volume is the difference in the added mass. The control volume shown in fig. 4.

FIGURE 4. A sphere that filled by liquid is moving through a fluid. The label m_a is showing the added mass circles (ellipse) are showing the expansion of the sphere. The support system is not shown.

The mass balance assumes incompressible material utiliz-

ing (Bar-Meir 2022a) reads

$$\frac{d(m_a + m_b)}{dt} = m_{in} - m_{out} \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, the added mass and body are strongly tied because both depend the body's diameter. The body mass is

$$m_b(t) = \frac{4\rho_b\pi(r_b)^3}{3} \quad (9)$$

while the added mass of the sphere (Bar-Meir 2022a) is

$$m_a(t) = \frac{2\rho_a\pi(r_b)^3}{3} \quad (10)$$

Notice here the derivation deviates from Giorgio et al as there no reason to ignore the change of body mass. Additionally, this consideration is not adding much more work and body density, in most cases, is comparable with the fluid density. Thus, the net mass change of the control volume is

$$\frac{d(m_a + m_b)}{dt} = \frac{2\pi(r_b)^2(\rho_a + 2\rho_b)}{3} \frac{dr_b}{dt} \quad (11)$$

To examine the effect of the change of the added mass it is assumed a flexible supply of liquid is attached to sphere. Thus, this situation does not a create force in the x direction. The net flow can be combined as a single stream. While the reasoning are omitted here and even maybe not be accurate physically, yet this examination provides an opportunity to check the effect of the added mass change. The added mass and not the biology is at the focus here, and thus jet is omitted. The momentum balance reads (Bar-Meir 2022a) where the gravity and shear forces are neglected due to symmetry and orientation (shear forces due to ideal flow assumption) as

$$\sum \mathbf{F}_{ext} - \int_{c.v.} \mathbf{P} dA = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \mathbf{U} \rho dV + \int_{c.v.} \rho \mathbf{U} U_m dA \quad (12)$$

The pressure term vanishes because D'Alembert's paradox and indifferent towards the symmetry around the body. The last term on the right is zero because there no flow out. Hence, eq. (12) is reduced into

$$\sum \mathbf{F}_{ext} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \mathbf{U} \rho dV = \mathbf{U} \frac{d}{dt} \int_{c.v.} \rho dV \quad (13)$$

It is assumed that the added mass and the body have to be with the same velocity and the uniform density. Additionally, the mass in control volume is expressed

$$\sum \mathbf{F}_{ext} = \mathbf{U} \frac{2\pi (r_b)^2 (\rho_a + 2\rho_b)}{3} \frac{dr_b}{dt} \quad (14)$$

There are several points that has to be emphasized. The equation similar to Giorgio et al's equation reduced version of eq. (14). During the derivations the symmetry was assumed thus for none symmetrical bodies there are additional terms that have accounted for which include the movement (velocity) of the boundary.

Regular bodies have mass and moment of inertia and thus the bodies have momentum and angular momentum. It is proposed here to include, beside the added mass and added moment of inertia, the added momentum and the added angular momentum. The added momentum should be defined

$$\text{added momentum} = m_a U \quad (15)$$

and the added angular momentum

$$\text{added momentum} = I_a \omega^2 \quad (16)$$

Notice that the angular moment also requires the definition of the pivot point as it is meaningless without it. The usage of the added momentum was demonstrated by Giorgio.

Concluding Remarks

It was shown that energy is not conserved in the case of change of added mass. The added mass change can be caused by three different mechanisms. All the three mechanisms create a need for a new term on the right hand side which depends on the reason for added mass change. The ideas that present in this paper are significant to the many questions of aquatic bodies and to surface vehicles. This paper is only preliminary examination of this topic. It is clear that these ideas should further explored.

Appendix A: The Governing Equations of Floating Bodies

The derivation in the paper the gravity effects were neglected. The purpose of this appendix is to demonstrate that the gravity can be combined with the equations above. The demonstration

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FIGURE 5. Forced Buoy

to show that the equation are similar and thus can be added to the terms above. While the derivation could be done in the same time, it does not provide clarity as a bare presentation.

A floating buoy has placed on a liquid and it is in equilibrium and the location of the gravity centroid is denoted as $x = 0$. The buoy movement up from the equilibrium a distance x is considered positive (that is not the coordinate x but the distance x). The external forces that act on buoy are resistance that is opposite to the velocity and the buoyancy that is negative in this case as buoy moves up. The buoyancy is difference from the equilibrium that is $x A \rho_\ell g$ in downward direction. In this statement, the derivation is for a constant cross section. The residence is opposite the direction of the velocity and hence it also downward. The internal force is up.

$$-x A \rho_\ell g - R \frac{dx}{dt} = (m_a + m_b) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} \quad (17)$$

or after small manipulation as

$$x A \rho_\ell g + R \frac{dx}{dt} + (m_a + m_b) \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = 0 \quad (18)$$

The buoyancy energy is $x^2 \rho_\ell g / 2$ and hence it can be written

$$\frac{x^2 \rho_\ell g}{2} + \frac{(m_a + m_b)}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 = C \quad (19)$$

which is similar to the equation that was discussed earlier with lost energy keep energy and some in between.

Notice that the formality requires that gravity force should that added mass should be part of the buoyancy potential however, it is canceled out and the net effect is the same.

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About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author's models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar-Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared any the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar-Meir's book. Dr. Spyrou's behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar-Meir's calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to copy Bar-Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes). Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to the discoveries of this author.

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Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar-Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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